

THOUGHT AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract

The article adequately covers the content and essence of the philosophical views of the enlightened scholar and thinker Abdulla Avloni, who is famous among Eastern thinkers for his new science.

Keywords: education, upbringing, morality, will and freedom.

Artificial intelligence is usually interpreted as the ability of automatic systems to take over individual functions of the human mind, for example, to make choices and make optimal decisions based on a rational analysis of previously acquired experience and external influences. Intelligence is the ability of the brain to solve problems by acquiring, memorizing and purposefully changing knowledge through learning from experience and adapting to different situations. The term "knowledge" is understood as information that comes to the brain through the sense organs, but is not sufficient for mental activity, since the objects of the environment surrounding us have the property not only to affect the sense organs, but also to interact with each other in a certain way. Therefore, in order to carry out intellectual activity in the environment, the knowledge system must have a model of this world. In this information model of the environment, real objects, their properties and the relationships between them are not only displayed and remembered, but can also be "purposefully changed" mentally. What is meant by an intellectual task? To explain how an intellectual task differs from a simple one, it is necessary to introduce the term "algorithm". In the old interpretation, an algorithm is a set of specific instructions describing the sequence of actions of a specific performer to achieve a result, solve a specific problem in a limited time. With the development of parallelism in computer work, the word "sequence" began to be replaced by the more general word "order". This is because some actions of an algorithm must be performed only one after the other, but some can be independent. The word "algorithm" comes from the Latin form of the name of the great mathematician of the 9th century, Al-Khwarizmi, who formulated the rules for performing arithmetic operations. Initially, algorithms were understood only as rules for performing four arithmetic operations on multi-digit numbers. Later, this concept began to be used in general, to indicate the sequence of actions that lead to the solution of a given problem. Finding algorithms is the main goal of a person in solving

various problems. Finding an algorithm for a given type of problem involves subtle and complex thinking that requires great ingenuity and high skill. It is generally accepted that this type of activity requires the participation of human intelligence. Problems related to finding an algorithm for solving a class of problems of a certain type are called intellectual. M. Minsky, a well-known expert in the field of artificial intelligence, argues that it is not necessary to introduce such a mystical feature as intelligence into problems for which solution algorithms are already established. Indeed, if the algorithm is already known, the process of solving the corresponding problems can be carried out precisely by a person or a computer without the slightest idea of the essence of the problem. The person solving the problem is required to be able to perform the elementary operations that make up the process. Brain activity aimed at solving intellectual problems is nothing more than thinking or intellectual activity. Intelligence and thinking are operationally related to solving problems such as proving theorems, logical analysis, recognizing situations, planning actions, playing games and managing in conditions of uncertainty. The characteristic features of intelligence that manifest themselves in the process of solving problems are the ability to learn, generalize, accumulate experience and adapt to changing conditions in the process of solving problems. Thanks to these qualities of intelligence, the brain can solve a variety of problems, and also easily switch from one problem to another. Thus, a brain endowed with intelligence is a universal tool for solving a wide range of problems for which there are no standard, pre-known solutions. The sad truth is that some people differ from thinking machines only in that they do not think about anything for a long time

The field of science called artificial intelligence explores the most mysterious questions of human existence. What is the nature of thinking? What processes occur in our bodies when we think, feel, see, and understand? How is this possible in principle? Are our brains melting? For thousands of years, man has been asking himself these questions, but he still cannot give them a clear answer. The term "intelligence" comes from the Latin word *intellectus*, which means mind, intelligence, reason; the ability of a person to think. Accordingly, research in the field of artificial intelligence has provided us with a new tool for studying these questions - the computer. Anyone who has worked with a computer will agree that a machine often creates more problems than it solves. However, for the study of the process of thinking, it is only useful. How can we imagine thinking? Imitation of thought was proposed by A. Turing. "In trying to imitate the intelligence of an adult," he wrote, "we are forced to think a lot about

how the human brain got to its present state... Why don't we try to create a program that imitates the intelligence of a child, instead of creating a program that imitates the intelligence of an adult? computing is such that a device similar to it can be easily programmed... Thus, we divide our problem into two parts: the problem of building a "child program" and the problem of "teaching" this program. Computers help us understand the nature of cognitive processes, first of all, by allowing us to test theoretical assumptions about how the brain works. Such theories are usually formulated as descriptions of ongoing processes. For example, when trying to understand how a person gets an answer to a question, one can assume that the question is first translated into an "internal representation"; then, using this "internal representation" as a kind of index, a person finds the necessary information in memory, converts it into a form convenient for the answer, and then translates it into words. It would seem that such descriptions very well reflect the processes that can occur in the mind . However, what at first glance looks like a completely satisfactory description turns out to be , as a rule, very imperfect . The processes associated with memorizing a fact can be clarified by the phrase: "... using the internal representation as an index, find the information stored in memory ..." How are facts recalled from memory? How is this memory organized? How does the brain cope with large amounts of information? If a programmer tries to write a program on such a primitive theoretical basis, he immediately faces these and many other questions. That is why writing programs is useful: they require clarity of presentation, and this, in turn, encourages us to delve deeper into theoretical ideas. Based on our definitions, the profession of a programmer is one of the most intellectual professions, since the product of a programmer's activity is programs, algorithms in their pure form. Therefore, the creation of even elements of artificial intelligence should significantly increase his work efficiency. Artificial intelligence is a small part of a huge attempt to understand thinking as a field of science and philosophy. This is perhaps the main goal of this field , and great success has already been achieved here. The main interest is not its artificial origin, but precisely the mind. If we succeed in this direction, we will open the way to creating mechanical assistants in the daily work and concerns of a person. But the most important thing that can be achieved is a deeper understanding of one's self, which is certainly more valuable than any program.

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